

HIGH STRAIN RATE TESTING OF FIBROUS COMPOSITE USING THE SPLIT HOPKINSON BAR TECHNIQUE WITH DIC

Amos Gilat, Jeremy Seidt

*Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
The Ohio State University, Columbus, OH.*

gilat.1@osu.edu

www.mecheng.osu.edu/lab/dmm/

Peiyu Yang ,Yogesh Deshpande,
Mark Konieczny

Department of Mechanical Engineering

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Lecture Outline:

- Introduction
- SHB Background
- Compression
- Tension

Split Hopkinson Bar (Kolsky) Technique

Compression

Tension

Torsion

T800/F3900 Unidirectional Laminate

Compression Split Hopkinson Bar (Kolsky) Technique

Notch depth: 0.02"

Compression Split Hopkinson Bar (Kolsky) Technique

Compression SHB Row Data

(T800/F3900 Composite 0° Compression)

Incident Bar Gage A, Loading Wave

Incident Bar Gage A, Reflected Wave

Transmitter bar Gage B

Incident bar Gage A reflected wave (Strain Rate)

T800/F3900 Composite 0° Compression SHB

Strain Measured with DIC

Stress, Strain, Strain Rate vs Time

T800/F3900 Composite 0° Compression

Compression SHB Row Data

(T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression)

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression SHB

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression SHB

Strain Measured with DIC

(T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression)

Stress, Strain, Strain Rate vs Time

(T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression)

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Compression

Tensile Split Hopkinson Bar (Kolsky) Technique

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Tension

Tension SHB Row Data

(T800/F3900 Composite 90° Tension)

Tensile 90° Split Hopkinson Bar (Kolsky) Test

Tensile 90° Split Hopkinson Bar (Kolsky) Test

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Tension, SHB DIC Strain

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Tension SHB Test

T800/F3900 Composite 90° Tension, Strain Rate

Conclusions:

The Digital Image Correlation (DIC) can be used for measuring the specimen strain when testing composites at high strain rates with the Split Hopkinson Bar (SHB) technique.

Results from testing in compression and tension show that there is a significant difference between the strain that is determined from the recorded waves in the bars and the strain that is measured on the surface of the specimen with the DIC technique.

Thank You!

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